

ISic0611

I.Sicily inscription 0611

Language

Latin

Type

milestone

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Philosophiana

Place of origin (modern)

near Mazzarino

Provenance

Sofiana (37.31424, 14.29943)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, (near) Mazzarino

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644871

Bibliography

- Li Gotti, A. 1955. Note su Philosophiana e Calloniana alla luce di nuovi rinvenimenti archeologici. *Archivio Storico Siciliano*. ser.III vol.7: 241-252. At 247
- Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 11 n.31
- Verbrugge, G.P. 1976. *Itinera Romana: Sicilia*. Berne. At 83 n.40

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0611. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385066>